

Cadomian and Variscan sutures of Iberia: a comparison

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The Iberian Massif holds evidence of two pre-Mesozoic orogenies, namely the Cadomian and Variscan. The Cadomian Orogeny resulted from long-lived subduction under the periphery of Gondwana during the Neoproterozoic and early Paleozoic (Murphy & Nance 1989). The Variscan Orogen resulted from the progressive collision of Gondwana, Laurussia and their pericontinental terranes during the Devonian and Carboniferous, after the closure of the Rheic Ocean and other marginal basins located along their mainlands (Díez Fernández et al. 2016). Despite these two orogens differ from one another in the global context from which they emerged, in Iberia they share some characteristics that make them intriguingly alike.

The Variscan Orogen contains two major suture zones. One that separates mainland Gondwana from peri-Gondwanan terranes (intra-Gondwana suture), and another one separating Laurussia from the latter terranes (Rheic suture) (Díez Fernández et al. 2016). The Variscan intra-Gondwana suture is tectonically dismembered and separates a collection of terranes with continental crust affinity that were transported inland from the periphery of Gondwana during the closure of a (Devonian) marginal basin opened during ongoing convergence between Gondwana and Laurussia (e.g., Careón Ophiolite), ~15 million years after the onset of the Variscan Orogen (Arenas et al. 2016). This process was the result of subduction polarity towards Laurussia, i.e. away from mainland Gondwana (Díez Fernández et al. 2012). The exhumation of the ophiolites and high-P rocks in this suture was largely controlled by syn-convergence extensional tectonics (Martínez Catalán et al. 2014). The current structure of the Rheic suture, on the other hand, is the result of reworking after the opening of an ephemeral oceanic basin (Beja-Acebuches Ophiolite; Azor et al. 2008). Subduction polarity during both the closure of the primary suture zone (Díez Fernández et al. 2016) and the closure of the ephemeral basin were beneath mainland Gondwana (Pérez-Cáceres et al. 2015). However, the closure of the ephemeral basin developed flake tectonics and obduction of pieces of the ocean basin onto the upper plate (Pérez-Cáceres et al. 2015).

Suture zones in the Cadomian Orogen went unnoticed until few years ago (Arenas et al. 2018; Díez Fernández et al. 2021). Despite being intensely reworked by Variscan deformation, the ongoing structural, tectonometamorphic, geochemical and geochronological studies provide first-order constraints on their primary (Cadomian) geometry as well as insight on the paleogeographic location of subduction zones that led to their formation. A collective, yet preliminary analysis of these sutures, pictures a major architecture of the Cadomian Orogen that contain, at least, two suture zones. One Cadomian suture is identified in the Mérida Ophiolite, which separates an upper and lower plate, both with continental crust affinity and likely Gondwanan derivation (intra-Gondwana suture). This intra-Gondwana suture was formed after the closure by subduction away from mainland Gondwana of a marginal basin that opened during ongoing convergence between Gondwana and an oceanic plate, millions of years after the onset of the Cadomian Orogen (Díez Fernández et al. 2021). The exhumation of the ophiolite and mid-P rocks that make this suture was largely controlled

by syn-convergence extensional tectonics (Díez Fernández et al. 2021). Another Cadomian suture is represented by the Calzadilla Ophiolite, whose protoliths formed in a fore-arc basin to the most external part of Gondwana (Arenas et al. 2018). The location of this suture zone is explained by flake tectonics, which contributed to the obduction of the ophiolite onto the upper plate while ongoing subduction was beneath mainland Gondwana (Díez Fernández et al. 2019).

Cadomian and Variscan sutures share fundamental characteristics regarding the paleolocation of the ocean basins they derive from and the overall resulting geometry and tectonic processes involved in their formation. The suture zones that represent the closure of basins located at the outermost section of peri-Gondwana, and closely facing subduction underneath Gondwana (Calzadilla and Beja-Acebuches ophiolites), were obducted inwards onto mainland Gondwana (upper plate). The intra-Gondwana suture zones (Careón and Mérida ophiolites) formed after subduction of a marginal basin beneath the periphery of Gondwana, and the exhumation of rock units of the subduction system was largely assisted by syn-convergence extensional tectonics following subduction-accretion. The Variscan and Cadomian orogens, despite being formed in different contexts (oceanic subduction vs. continental collision), share two major features. Both are (i) mostly built by Gondwanan lithosphere, and (ii) occupy the upper plate of a subduction zone that consumed a large ocean. These two orogens alternate phases of contraction and extension (mostly concentrated in the upper plate). In both cases, extension was intense enough as to create marginal ocean basins and to favor exhumation of deep-seated rocks (quite common in upper plates). Perhaps, these major features they share may explain the resemblance of the final global architecture of these two orogens, and provide additional arguments to consider Gondwana as resistant to subduction and recycling in the mantle and prone to crustal growth, being the upper plate to the orogenic systems it was involved in during at least 300 m.y.

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